

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL SERVICE IN MODERN CARE

Ahmed.K.Ahasani¹, Zayed.S.Alzhranae², Mohammad.H.Alharbi³, Moataz.S.Kardawi⁴,
Fawaz.S.Alkhuzaee⁵, Fairuoz.M.Shabanah⁶, Hussein.S.Alzahrani⁷, Rania.
O.Alobairi⁸, Fahad.I.Jawni⁹, Wed.A.Alhantoshi¹⁰, Suaad.A.Jamae¹¹

Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca¹Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca²Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca³Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca⁴Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca⁵Social worker at King Faisal Hospital in Mecca⁶Social worker in Alsharaya health sector⁷Social worker at the primary healthcare center in Al-Deifah⁸Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca⁹Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca¹⁰Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca¹¹**Abstract:**

The aim of the study is, the role of social service in modern community service care, the role of social service in using modern technology to serve society, the impact of the social worker on the souls of patients in society. A questionnaire was created and designed via Google Drive and distributed on the social media network (WhatsApp) to health practitioners and practices in Mecca 800 questionnaires were distributed and responses were obtained to 750 questionnaires from the targeted targets (Residents of Makkah aged 25-60 years).

Keywords: role of social service, modern care

Corresponding author:**Ahmed.K.Ahasani,**

Social worker at King Abdulaziz Hospital in Mecca

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ahmed.K.Ahasani et al., *The Role Of Social Service In Modern Care*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2023; 10 (12).

1-INTRODUCTION:

Social services are a set of public services that aim to supply sustain and help to special groups, which usually contain harm groups (financially or health-wise) ⁽¹⁾. These groups can extradiate support from persons or private, separate organizations, or administrated by a government institution. Social services are related to the concept of social welfare and the welfare state, and countries with large social welfare programs often provide a wide range of social services ⁽²⁾. Social services are appointing to meet a wide range of community needs. Before industrialization, the condition of social services was largely limited to particular organizations and charities, with their scope of coverage also limited ⁽³⁾. Social services are now generally saw as a “necessary job” of society, and a mechanism through which governments can address societal issues ⁽⁴⁾. Governments' provision of social services is related to belief in universal human rights and democratic principles, in addition to religious and cultural values. The availability and coverage of social services varies widely within communities ⁽⁵⁾. Social service's major aim is to develop societies by searching for the different forces and agents that stop social growth and progress, such as deprivation, unemployment, illness, and poor living case that are beyond the ability of the individuals who pain from them and that work to make them miserable. It also searches for the reason of sick's in society in order to address and hostilities them. These source and the most suitable and active means are choice in society to clear them or decreased their impact and the destroy that outcomes from them to the minimum possible range ⁽⁶⁾. Social service aims. Preventive targets. Therapeutic objectives. Development purposes. Social service's main aim is to develop societies, by searching for the different forces and factors that stop growth and social progress, such as deprivation, unemployment, disease, and bad living conditions, which are beyond the area of the individuals who stick from them and which make them miserable. It also searches for the impact of evils. In society in order to be facing and combat these reasons and select the most appropriate and influence means in society to remove them or minimize their effects and the harm that scores from them to the minimum possible extent. The philosophy of social service is based on the basic pillars: belief in the value and dignity of the individual and belief in individual differences, whether between individuals, societies or groups. Belief in the right of the individual to exercise his freedom within the limits of societal values. The individual's right to self-determination without harming the rights of others. Social service believes in social justice between one gender and another or

between one religion and another. She believes in love and tolerance. It believes that the human being is the single energy in bringing about social modify and for his well-being, while helping him carry out the social turns that prevent him from performing them, such as the role of the head of the family in production and work ⁽⁶⁾. There are three general kinds or levels linked to the nature of the general practice of social work, which we will list below. The first phase is the level of main units of general social work practice, which involves dealing from a comprehensive perspective with society or societies as a whole. This level we are dealing with contains setting social policy that aims to hold off rights at the national or international level. The second phase is defined as the level of intermediate units of general practice in social work. This level includes working with small bodies, organizations and other small groups. This level of general practice contains developing policies within the framework of a body specialized in social work and providing social services, or developing and activating programs for a neighboring community. The third and final level is the level of tiny units of general practice, which includes providing services to individuals and families. There are many activities that are widely practiced, the most serious of which are those representing social work, as social workers work with multiple formats in most various settings. In general, social workers who attract in clinical or manage social work practice work at the micro-unit level of social work. As for social workers who work in the area of general practice, they work at the level of medium or large units of social work. Below are lists detailing a number of kinds of tasks that social workers may work in. Regarding the use of modern technologies in social service, there are studies that have confirmed the following: This is what was confirmed by a study ⁽⁷⁾, This study leads that electronic therapy requires training social workers on the hands of specialists on how to use electronic therapy in social service, and the theory indicates, Innovation means that it is in order to enhance the use of electronic therapy or any other technological means in Practicing social service: training social workers and providing supervisors must begin Specialists, and training should focus on electronic therapy skills through emphasizing the responsibilities of social workers, such as (emphasizing securing data and information -Benefits and aspects of applying this innovation). The General Administration of Psychological and Social Health recently issued a guide to policies and procedures for medical social service, which is a document concerned with medical social service, which is one of the fields of social service. Its objectives are harnessed within medical, health and rehabilitation institutions for preventive,

curative and developmental aims, practiced by qualified and trained specialists in the health field, and it has a strong, complementary relationship with other health and medical fields. This leader was ready after reviewing the experiences of leading countries in this field to develop and improve the social service provided to patients and their families in accordance with quality rules and indicators ⁽⁸⁾.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The is begun in (the holy city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), writing the research and then recording the questionnaire in June 2023, and the study ended with data collection in October 2023. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the social phenomenon (The role of social service in modern care). This kind of study is characterized by analysis, reason, objectivity, and reality, as it is concerned with individuals and societies, as it studies the variables and their effects on the health of the individual, society, and consumer, the spread of diseases and their relationship to demographic variables such as age, gender, nationality, and marital status. Status, occupation ⁽⁹⁾, And use the Excel 2010 Office suite histogram to arrange the results using: Frequency tables Percentages ⁽¹⁰⁾. A questionnaire is a remarkable and helpful tool for collecting a huge amount of data, however, researchers were not able to personally interview participants on the online survey, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent infection between participants and researchers and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only answered the questionnaire electronically, because the questionnaire consisted of ten questions, five questions were opened, and five questions were closed. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere.

3- RESULTS:

The percentage of participation by the targeted participants in the research questionnaire (residents of the city of Mecca) was 25-60 years old. Their participation rate was as follows: from 25-34 years old, 33.3%, and from 35-44 years old, 44.4%. Age 45-54 years 22.2%, no participation from those aged 55-60 years. As for the gender of the participants, the percentage of males participating in the questionnaire was 61.1%, and the percentage of females was 38.9%, and all of their nationalities were 100% Saudi. Their occupations were distributed as follows: student 22.2%, government employee 55.6%, private sector employee 11.1%, housewife 0%, self-employed 0%. As for their educational status, their educational qualifications were as follows: neither see nor write

0%, primary 0%, middle school 0%, secondary school 0%, diploma 5.6%, university 72.2%, master's 22.2%, doctorate 0%. Its primary goal is to support members of society and achieve justice for them, in addition to developing communities and working to find an appropriate balance between members of society, overcoming obstacles, and finding appropriate solutions to achieve this. communication and facilitation, It works to help the individual, the group and society, Social service helps the community solve its problems, Humanitarian service for those seeking assistance, serving the community and patients and coordinating between families, associations and government departments to serve the client, Social service is a science, art, skill, and scientific profession based on helping individuals, groups, and society to solve the problems and difficulties they face in order to perform their social roles and adapt to their society and environments. A group of public services that aim to provide support and assistance to specific groups, A humanitarian profession practiced by specialized social workers to help people solve their problems, A field that aims to provide support and assistance to individuals and communities facing social difficulties or lack of opportunities, help the community, Studying everything that affects an individual's life and its impact on society, the meaning of social service is serving the community and those who need help from social workers, social work or social service is an academic discipline and practice-based profession that concerns individuals, families, and communities in an effort to enhance social functioning and overall well-being. Social work is the way people perform their social roles, and the structural institutions that are provided to support them. Developing societies through belief in the individual's values and freedom within the values of society a big role

Social service aims to help individuals and improve their lives, Providing therapeutic and social services and psychological and moral support, and it has a role in confronting and responding to problems, Effectively, Improving the severity of life, It contributes to the development and adaptation of society, Social service's main goal is to develop societies by searching for the various forces and factors that prevent social growth and progress, such as deprivation, unemployment, disease, and poor living conditions that are beyond the ability of the individuals who suffer from them and that work to make them miserable. It also searches for the causes of ills in society in order to address and combat them. These reasons. Solving community problems, preventing problems and damages, raising awareness and providing guidance, Helping individuals and groups

achieve greater well-being and solve problems, Helping individuals and groups, Its role is to promote social justice and improve the quality of life of individuals and communities, Providing help to the community Searching for a solution o problems affecting the individual and society, Her role is to help anyone in the community who needs assistance from social workers. The third question is about: What is the role of the social worker in society? Studying individual and family cases and achieving solidarity in society, with an interest in linking individuals with the services of government and private institutions and introducing them to the services provided to them and benefiting from them. Achieving the principle of the right to self-determination for individuals. effective role Solving problems of individuals and groups, Providing support, confrontation and support, Be a researcher into community problems and find solutions, Revealing situations of weakness and strength and changing society for the better, An important role to transfer acquired skills and how to adapt to society. The role of the social worker is to organize the methods of social life within the school environment. Community service is one of the basic methods of the social service profession. Its goal is the growth of individuals within the group, the satisfaction of their social needs, and the achievement of their legitimate goals, in addition to creating a place that constitutes a source of happiness for students. Community service is based on experiences Children and their ideas, and making laws compatible with the needs of children within certain limits. The preventive and developmental role in serving the group. Social work with the group is one of the most beautiful and broadest ways that help social workers meet the needs of individuals through the work of dynamic groups that aim to satisfy the desires and needs of their owners. And strive to achieve their goals, in addition to their role in providing advice For parents, conducting educational courses to educate parents and children about many societal issues; Such as violence, alcohol, abuse, or other problems, The services that the social worker provides with the group. The following points explain the services that the social worker provides to the group, Social work with the group helps to provide support to individual students within one group; Thus, students support each other. This in turn helps teach the group and students how to accept others, provide assistance to those who need it, altruism, and many other good qualities that society must develop. The social worker helps give the group a sense of community and belonging, as well as cohesion as a bond. Developing the spirit of competition. Some bit them. Help solve everyone's concerns by observing and teaching them how to deal with problems.

Teaching them new skills and behaviors through creative activities, worksheets, etc. Helping them express their feelings and thoughts without any barriers or hesitation. Protective and developmental role, Achieving justice for all marginalized groups living in this society, helping them obtain their various rights, and providing them with all the special social services they need in all different fields. Guidance, counselling, psychological support, and providing therapeutic and preventive programs, Providing specialized services and support to individuals and communities, Helping the community achieve its goals, Activate and implement the proposed solutions and follow them up, His role is important in society, as he helps society solve its problems and helps those who have problems with it. The fourth question is about preventive, therapeutic and environmental, a big role preventive, curative and developmental, Preventive and curative, Preventive, therapeutic and developmental goals, Change, participation and solutions

Development goals, treatment goals, and prevention goals, The most important goal is for the client to feel adaptable to his family, his community, and the outside world, The goal of social service as a specialized profession is to make people happy and achieve their well-being. When social systems are unable to satisfy people's needs, social service intervenes to help these systems perform their functions. As for the method, it follows specific and effective methods to achieve its desired goals. These methods depend on skill, and they require preparation. Personally and during practice. Curative, preventive and developmental, Community development, Helping individuals adapt to their situations, It aims to support and assist individuals who suffer from social difficulties such as poverty, violence, and discrimination, Developing society and achieving well-being in life , Helping the individual and society to coexist in a problem-free environment, Its goals are to help any member of society solve their problems and help with them in solving them. The fifth question: Is social service limited to solving family problems only? Yes 5.6% and no 94.4%. The sixth question: Does social service actually play a major role in solving problems? The answers were all 100% yes. The seventh question about: Realizing the principle of equality and the individual's right to full care and benefit from available resources to produce a healthy environment, Integrity, They all care about the individual and meet his requirements, meeting human needs, service under the care policy

Social care is part of social service, they have a strong relationship, they both care about humans and their requirements. the use of social workers in many social

care institutions in planning and professional work. Social care institutions are an environment for practicing social service. Social service helps introduce innovation in social welfare activities, A relational relationship, which is social care for all segments of society, individuals, groups and society. They all care about people and their demands, Social care stems from social service, Social service works to provide support and assistance to individuals and communities, while social care aims to provide care and protection for individuals who suffer from difficult or inappropriate conditions, and this may include housing, food, health care, and education, Providing assistance to a person, Convergence of views, Their relationship is important as their relationship is interconnected and complements each other. The eighth question: Do you know what digital social service means? The answer was yes 55.6% and no 44.4%. The ninth question: What interactive programs does a social worker use in his work: computers, Internet networks, smart phone applications? Yes 94.4% and no 5.6%. The tenth question about: By providing therapeutic services through digital communication channels such as Zoom, Skype, etc., through video communication or through providing remote consultations.

Imam ,Employing digital communication networks in individual or family treatments, The social worker

conducts therapeutic interviews online, by phone, or by email. Diagnosis and treatment Providing consultations. The digital platform stimulates and summarizes the specialist's work and the most important achievements he has made. Employing digital communication networks in individual or family treatments: This type of digital treatment aims to employ Internet networks in therapeutic interviews, where the social worker conducts therapeutic interviews over the Internet, over the phone, or via email, or using digital technology applications such as chat programs such as WhatsApp. Telegram is used for conducting group interviews, especially when a family member is out of the home for a long period. Such as a husband or a student in family therapy who wants this member to participate in family therapeutic interviews as it is an important form of family interaction. Thus, with the social service employing these digital means, there is always an opportunity for treatment at any time and in any place. Practicing social service using computers and mobile devices, such as studying cases, doing social psychological assessments, following up on cases, and virtual clinics using the Internet, computers, and social service statistics. training courses. Evaluation and diagnosis - planning and implementation - guidance and guidance - coordination and cooperation, Questionnaire Identify problems and address them, Computer where you need statistics.(figure No.1)

Figure No.1: Through the opinions of participants in the research questionnaire, about the role of social service in modern care, actually solving societal problems

4-DISCUSSION:

We conclude from this study that, through the responses of the participants in the research questionnaire, we find that they all value the role and importance of social service, and the role of the social worker in society by providing support to families in need, and solving their family problems using modern technology and methods of social communication.

Acknowledgment:

To start with, I would like to Praise God and thank Dr. Anas S. Dablood, from Umm Al-Qura University (Public Health Department, Faculty of Health Sciences Al-leeth), Mecca, Saudi Arabia. And the researchers who make the project come to light.

REFERENCES:

- 1- EUROPEAN SOCIAL SERVICES". scholar.googleusercontent.com. Archived from the original on 10/01/2022. Accessed on 06/01/2021.
- 2- Seekings, Jeremy; Natrass, Nicoli (2015), "The Welfare State, Public Services and the 'Social Wage'", Developmental Pathways to Poverty Reduction, London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, p. 162–184, DOI:10.1057/9781137452696_7, ISBN:978-1-349-56904-5, archived from the original on 2022-10-05, accessed on 2021-06-02.
- 3- Pierson, Chris (2004), "'Late Industrializers' and the Development of the Welfare State", Social Policy in a Development Context, London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, p. 215–245, DOI:10.1057/9780230523975_10, ISBN:978-1-4039-3661-5, archived from the original on 2022-10-20, accessed on 2021-06-01.
- 4- Social service". Encyclopedia Britannica (in English). Archived from the original on 2023-02-17. Retrieved 2021-06-01.
- 5- Peng, Ito; Wong, Joseph (July 15, 2010). "East Asia". Oxford Handbooks Online. DOI:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199579396.003.004 5. Archived from the original on 2021-06-03
- 6- Introduction to the social service profession, written by specialist: Nahla Rabah from Palestine - Social Sciences Journal Forum ~ Archived copy August 5, 2017 on the Wayback Machine website.
- 7- Julie Cwikel, Enav Friedmann (2019): E-therapy and social work practice: Benefits, barriers, and training, International Social Work.
- 8- <https://www.moh.gov.sa/Portal/WhatsNew/Pages/Whatsnew-2016-06-14-001.aspx>
- 16- Alserahy, Hassan Awad, et al (2008), The thinking and scientific research, Scientific Publishing Center, King Abdul-Aziz University in Jeddah, the first edition
- 17- Al Zoghbi, Muhammad and AlTalvah, Abas (2000), Statistical system understanding and analysis of statistical data, first edition, Jordon-Amman
- 18-. Kadasah, N.A.; Chirwa, G.C.; et al. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Toward COVID-19 Among the Public in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Study. Front. Public Health 2020, 8, 217.